

$P_{\text{egger}} = 0.898$, Estimated missing = 0, Feed Intake

$P_{\text{egger}} = 0.630$, Estimated missing = 22, Laying Rate

$P_{\text{egger}} = 0.970$, Estimated missing = 0, Feed-to-Egg Ratio

$P_{\text{egger}} = 0.424$, Estimated missing = 0, Egg Weight

$P_{\text{egger}} = 0.891$, Estimated missing = 5, Haugh Unit

$P_{\text{egger}} = 0.174$, Estimated missing = 20, Shell Thickness

Supplement-1: Funnel plot and Egger’s test for publication bias on the effect of quercetin treatments on production, egg quality, blood metabolites, and anti-oxidant defence in laying hens. $P_{\text{egger}} < 0.05$ and asymmetry Funnel plots demonstrate high risk publication bias.